

Synthesis of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,4-dioxo-7-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substituted-phenyl-5H-pyrano-[2,3-d]-pyrimidines and 3-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substituted-phenylisoxazoles

C. S. Andotra*, Jatinder Khajuria and Sukhbinder Kaur

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 006, Jammu & Kashmir, India

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Abstract : 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dioxo-7-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substitutedphenyl-5H-pyrano-[2,3-d]-pyrimidines were prepared by condensing chalcones with barbituric acid in glacial acetic acid in presence of P_2O_5 and 3-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substitutedphenylisoxazoles were prepared by adding Br_2 dissolved in chloroform dropwise to cold solutions of 1-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-3-substituted phenylprop-2-en-1-one on stirring to obtain the dibromoderivatives. Ethanolic solution of dibromoderivatives were refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of aqueous KOH to get the required compounds.

Keywords : Heterocyclic compounds, oxadiazoles.

In continuation of our earlier^{1,2} work on the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds we report here synthesis of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-2,4-dioxo-7-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substitutedphenyl-5H-pyrano-[2,3-d]-pyrimidines³ and 3-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substitutedphenylisoxazoles. The oxadiazoles derivatives and various substituted pyrimidine are known to possess various biological activities like anti-inflammatory⁴⁻⁷, antibacterial^{8,9}, CNS^{10,11} and analgesic activities and many more.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on Buchi melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded using KBr disc on Pye Unicam Sp-2000. PMR spectra were recorded in $DMSO-d_6$ on a DPX-200 (200 MHz) machine. The chemical shifts are measured in ppm units.

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-2,4-dioxo-7-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substitutedphenyl-5H-pyrano-[2,3-d]-pyrimidines (2) :

1-(2,4-Dialkoxyphenyl)-3-substitutedphenyl-2-en-1-one (0.005 mole) was dissolved in glacial acid and to this was added barbituric acid (0.006 mole) and phosphorous pentoxide (1 g). The content were stirred at 120 °C on oil bath for 2–3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and treated with crushed ice. The solid thus obtained was refluxed in water for 5–10 min and then filtered while hot. The m.p. and yield and spectral data of the compounds prepared are given in Table 1.

2,3-Dibromo-1-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substitutedphenylpropan-1-one (3) :

To a cold solution of 1-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substitutedphenylprop-2-en-1-one (0.005 mole) in chloroform. Br_2 (0.01 mole) dissolved in chloroform was added dropwise with constant stirring. The solvent was then removed on a steam bath. The resulting solid was washed with little cold ether to remove excess of bromine and

Table 1

Compd.	R	Ar	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	IR (cm ⁻¹)	NMR
2a	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	180–182	94	2950, 1676, 1605, 1260, 1190	1.25–1.45 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.9–4.2 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.0 Hz, <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.02 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.6–8.0 (8H, m, Ar- <i>H</i>), 10.8 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>), 11.6 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>)
2b	C ₂ H ₅	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃	145–147	87	2972, 1678, 1608, 1262, 1194	1.35–1.50 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.05–4.20 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.01 Hz, <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.02 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.6–8.0 (8H, m, Ar- <i>H</i>), 10.8 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>), 11.6 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>)
2c	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (OCH ₃) ₂ 3,4	190–191	87	2950, 1676, 1606, 1260, 1192	1.3–1.5 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.9–4.2 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.01 Hz, <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.02 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 5.9 (2H, s, OCH ₂ O), 6.2–8.0 (8H, m, Ar- <i>H</i>), 10.8 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>), 11.6 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>)
2d	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (OCH ₃) ₂ 3,4	204–206	89	2960, 1676, 1605, 1260, 1190	1.31–1.5 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.85 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 4.15–4.30 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.31 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.0 Hz, <i>H</i> -5), 5.81 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.03 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.2–8.0 (6H, m, Ar- <i>H</i>), 10.8 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>), 11.6 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>)
2e	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₃) ₂ (OCH ₃) 2,4	232–234	86	2950, 1676, 1605, 1260, 1190	1.28–1.48 (9H, t, 3 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.15–4.30 (6H, q, 3 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.91 Hz, <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.0 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.2–8.0 (6H, m, Ar- <i>H</i>), 10.8 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>), 11.6 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>)
2f	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ Cl-4	208–210	86	2950, 1676, 1605, 1260, 1190	1.32–1.52 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.0–4.2 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.01 Hz, <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.02 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.2–8.0 (7H, m, Ar- <i>H</i>), 10.8 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>), 11.6 (1H, s, <i>NH</i>)

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

2g	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃)-4	220-222	84	2950, 1676, 1605, 1260, 1190	1.3-1.5 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.34 (3H, s, CH ₃), 4.0-4.15 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.01 Hz, <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.04 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.2-8.0 (7H, m, Ar-H), 10.8 (1H, s, NH), 11.6 (1H, s, NH)
2h	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (Cl) ₂ 2,4	225-227	88	2960, 1676, 1605, 1260, 1190	1.31-1.51 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.0-4.15 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.0 Hz, <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.02 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.2-8.0 (6H, m, Ar-H), 10.8 (1H, s, NH), 11.6 (1H, s, NH)
2i	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₃ (Cl) ₂ 2,4	210-212	85	2950, 1670, 1610, 1262, 1190	3.8 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.01 Hz <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.03 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.2-8.0 (6H, m, Ar-H), 10.8 (1H, s, NH), 11.6 (1H, s, NH)
2j	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₃ (Cl)(NO ₂) ₂ 2,5	185-187	88	2950, 1670, 1610, 1262, 1190	3.85 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 4.3 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.01 Hz <i>H</i> -5), 5.8 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 5.03 Hz, <i>H</i> -6), 6.2-8.0 (6H, m, Ar-H), 10.8 (1H, s, NH), 11.6 (1H, s, NH)

Table 2

Compd.	R	Ar	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	IR (cm ⁻¹)	NMR
4a	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	145-147	84	2980, 1603, 1260, 1192, 760, 690	1.2-1.4 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.2-4.4 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.8-8.2 (9H, m, H-4 and Ar-H)
4b	C ₂ H ₅	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ O CH ₃	180-182	83	3060, 1604, 1262, 1195, 760, 690	1.2-1.38 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.18-4.36 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.9-8.2 (8H, m, H-4 and Ar-H)
4c	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (O CH ₂ O) 3,4	178-179	81	3008, 1603, 1260, 1190, 750, 690	1.25-1.45 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.2-4.4 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.88 (2H, s, O-CH ₂ -O), 6.8-8.0 (7H, m, H-4 and Ar-H)
4d	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (O CH ₃ O) ₂ 3,4	175-177	81	3010, 1603, 1262, 1190, 750, 680	1.4-1.6 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.86 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 4.2-4.4 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.8-8.0 (7H, m, H-4 and Ar-H)

Table-2 (contd.)

4e	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₃) ₃ (OCH ₃) _{4,3}	140-142	79	3030, 1600, 1620, 1190, 760, 682	1.39-1.59 (9H, t, 3 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.0-4.24 (6H, q, 3 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.9-7.9 (7H, m, H-4 and Ar-H)
4f	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃) ₄	190-192	67	2870, 1640, 1262, 1195, 760, 690	1.24-1.46 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.95-4.25 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 7.10-8.20 (8H, m, H-4 and Ar-H)
4g	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ Cl-4	187-189	79	3100, 1605, 1260, 1190, 760, 690	1.23-1.43 (6H, t, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.2-4.4 (4H, q, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.9-8.02 (8H, m, H-4 and Ar-H)
4h	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₃ (Cl) ₂ 2,4	110-112	80	3080, 1605, 1260, 1195, 760, 690	3.8 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.8-8.2 (7H, m, H-4 and Ar-H)

then crystallized from ethanol.

3-(2,4-Dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substitutedphenylisoxazoles (4) :

Ethanol solution of 2,3-dibromo-1-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-3-substitutedphenylpropan-1-one (0.003 mole) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.006 mole). After a few minutes 30% aqueous KOH was added to it and refluxing continued till colour of the reaction mixture turned red with simultaneous deposition of potassium bromide. It was allowed to stand for 30 min at room temperature, cooled and acidified with dilute HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallized from alcohol. The m.p and yield and spectral data of the compounds prepared are given in Table 2.

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